

Financial Problems Met in the Tourism Sector in Turkey: A Survey on the Tourism Businesses

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Abstract—As the economies of other countries in the Mediterranean Basin, the tourism sector in our country has a high denominator in economics. Tourism businesses, which are building blocks of tourism, sector faces with a variety of problems during their activities. These problems faced make business efficiency and competition conditions of the businesses difficult. Most of the problems faced by the tourism businesses and the information of consumers about consumers' rights were used in this study, which is conducted to determine the problems of tourism businesses in the Central Anatolia Region. It is aimed to contribute the awareness of staff and executives working at tourism sector and to attract attention of businesses active concurrently with tourism sector and legislators.

Keywords—Financial Problems, The problems of Tourism businesses, Tourism Businesses, Tourism Sector in Turkey.

I. INTRODUCTION

SINCE the second half of the 20th century, tourism has become of the fastest developing and expanding sectors in the world economy. Tourism, as many other industries, is often used as a tool for local and national development. Tourism has taken its place as an important factor to form a widespread income, job and tax revenues, as moderating the balance of payments and contributing to local developments. In today's world, the tourism sector, one of the key sectors of our country's economy, makes its presence felt. There are some studies that aim to achieve a world standard in the tourism sector and increase the service quality. With the diversity in the tourism demand worldwide and the existence of tourism demand dependent on sea, sand, sun, trio, people in tourism activities do not contented with this trio. The Turkish tourism businesses and authorities who are aware of the situation try to build appropriate facilities and preparing a legal infrastructure. The businesses whose aim is only benefit and lack of qualified staff, which is a problem that is not cleared up, yet in Turkey and the studies made to protect foreign and domestic tourists are not enough. Tourists have no idea about how to solve the problems they face. However, high prices applied to domestic tourists devitalize them. Having unqualified top executives and not meeting the

demands of today's tourism disappoints the foreign tourists. This situation is distressful for the country advertising and image; also inadequate advertising of the country and wrong and weak usage of marketing are other problems tourism sector encounter. As well as not advertising the nature, destroying the natural beauties and building tall buildings on destroyed green areas also a problem encountered. At the same time, during the establishment of these facilities, the infrastructure of the environment the facility built on and not having a proper construction plan became an important factor. Consultation meetings were held to solve the indicated problems and solutions suggested for the current problems of tourism sector in our country. Academics and government executives attended these meetings and with their solution suggestions, improvements were made. In this study consisting of four sections, the subjects the legal, environmental and political problems and the main problem of facilities, employment, are discussed. The study was done using a questionnaire, which aims to find out the general problems of 25 tourism businesses in Central Anatolia region, and finished with a conclusion that has the evaluation.

II. TOURISM IN TURKEY

Turkey has become the sixth most visited country in the world after Italy with totally 31.5 million international visitors in 2011. Turkey's total revenue from international visitors was more than USD 28 billion in 2011. Business Monitor International forecasts revenues to exceed USD 35 billion by 2017. Oxford Economics outlook for the global economy is more optimistic for the coming years. As the global economy recovers, travel and tourism will increase. Improvements in the economies of European nations, for whom Turkey is a popular destination, will aid the growth of the travel and tourism industry. Business Monitor International indicates that Turkey, as an emerging market, will benefit greatly from the global economic recovery. The contribution of the travel and tourism industry to Turkey's GDP has a higher growth forecast compared to that of Europe. From 2013 to 2023, average growth is expected to remain around 3% for Turkey. Meanwhile in Europe, average growth from 2013 to 2023 is projected as approximately 2%. After 2010, the travel and tourism industry recovered strongly with a 19.5% rate of growth in 2011, significantly greater than the growth rate of the Turkish economy in that respective period. The reason for this fluctuation was domestic demand; capital investments and indirect revenues had decreased significantly in 2010 compared to 2009. However, the Turkish economy recovered in 2011 and the percentage of growth returned to higher levels.

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The industry also has a significant share of national employment. Starting from 2011, the industry gained strong upward momentum and is projected to increase through 2023. The contribution of the industry to employment is projected to increase from USD 2.1 billion to USD 2.5 billion, which is a 17% increase from 2013 to 2023. The travel and tourism industry generated a total of USD 85 billion through linkages with other sectors of the Turkish economy. The GDP of the travel and tourism industry in Turkey is greater than industries such as automotive manufacturing, communication services, financial services, mining, education and the manufacturing of chemicals. The travel and tourism industry has added totally 1.9 million jobs to the economy. It is the second largest employment provider after the public sector. Turkey is a popular tourist destination with an ever-increasing number of visitors. Despite the economic downturn in Europe, which is one of Turkey's biggest target markets, the number of international visitors increased slightly from 2011 to 2012, and 35% from 2007 to 2012, reaching more than 31.5 million foreign visitors. In 2012, a majority of visitors were German citizens. Six countries topped the list of arrivals, namely, Germany, Russia, the Ukraine, Bulgaria, Georgia and Iran which constituted around 79% of the total number of international visitors. The total visitor number, which includes citizens residing abroad and foreign visitors, increased 142% from 2002 to 2012 and 35% from 2007 to 2012. Turkey maintains healthy growth in the sector while the Middle East and North Africa have seen more of a negative impact. Business Monitor International forecasts that the international tourist arrival rate will grow rapidly reaching more than 37 million visitors in 2017. The number of Turkish citizens touring Turkey has also grown strongly from 2004-2012, having reached more than 6 million in 2012 [1].

III. THE EXPERIENCED LEGAL PROBLEMS AND SUGGESTIONS

In parallel with the development of information technology, goods and services are commercialized and sold on internet. The easiness of the shopping without seeing the seller and buyer, the owner of the goods and services market and sell their products on internet and consumers buy them. However, in parallel with the rapid technological progress, having no legal infrastructure in our country, ill wishers who take advantage of legal gap or the people who advertise tours and sell despite the fact that they do not have travel agency operating permit are seen. Domestic tourists who make online reservations or buy tours on internet for summer months are aggrieved and instead of sunbathing, they spend their time in front of TURSAB or tourism directorate. While illegal agencies are imposed sanctions, there is no enforcement at Internet Crimes Law for the ill-wishers who take domestic and foreign tourists in on internet [2].

In order to prevent these problems, the consumers are protected by law, but these kinds of businesses which are not operating on legal basement and called "illegal businesses" continue their activities at universities as travel community or at holiday resorts renting houses daily or weekly. Travel

agencies should buy insurance as part of packet tour in order to ensure their service and responsibilities to customers.

In addition, travel agencies are responsible for informing the customers about the insurance they will provide which include the return expenses and all the expenses for any kind of accident and treatment. Customer can demand his loss directly from the insurance agency. Travel agency should deliver packet tour insurance policy with package tour agreement [3].

Legal travel agencies should have a yellow brass plate carrying TURSAB emblem in order to show they are travel agency. Besides, these agencies should have an original Travel Agency Operating Document hung apparently. One of them or travel agency operating document should be shown when asked. Besides, writing the agency's name on www.tursab.org.tr the search can be done.

IV. THE EXPERIENCED FINANCIAL PROBLEMS AND SOLUTION ADVICES

In today's world, tourism sector is considered as one of the non-ignorable factors for economic growth and development of developed and developing countries [4]. Tourism sector in Turkey developed after 1980 with the incentives given and started to catch the growth trend in the world which lead this sector become an important sector in terms of income and employment. Determining the problems and solutions for these problems of travel and hotel businesses whose importance for the country is getting more and more important. Many problems can be mentioned about tourism sector which is easily affected by economic crisis, economic and politic fluctuations. However, when the special features of the sector considered, it is seen that financial problems can affect businesses negatively. Salaries and insurance premiums of this sector are very high because of limited automation at travel and hotel businesses and needs more labour. However, changes in touristic demands complicate making financial planning thus increase the risk of facing financial problems.

Reference [5] indicates the factors that lead financial distress according to their effect respectively; cost structure, occupancy rates, employment structure, number of beds, overnight, debt structure and inflation.

Small and medium scale businesses have an important place in the economy of the country with their less investment and more production and demanded product variety, contributing employment with lower investment cost, encouraging personal savings, completing the big scale businesses as a complement and being less affected from the economic fluctuations. Despite the contribution to the country's economy, SMEs face some problems as a result of either their structure or economic situation. These problems arise in all areas of the business.

As in the other sectors, financial problems affect tourism sector too. In a survey conducted in Alberta State, Canada, 41% of 400 businesses indicated that their success was affected from the financial problems [6]. According to the American Chamber of Commerce in Egypt, financial problem is the most important institutional factor that prevents their growth [6]. Tourism sector in Turkey is almost the same.

Small and medium scale tourism businesses have parallel problems with SMEs.

While worrying about continuing on the market, SMEs in our country struggle competing against the others. In order to survive SMEs need a strong equity or they should be financially strong. In the countries with economic fluctuations especially in Turkey, economic crisis makes the situation difficult. At that point, SMEs face many nested financial problems. There are four main reasons of these financial problems SMEs face in our country [7].

- Economic instability,
- Structural problems of the banking system,
- Lack of incentive policies,
- Problems arising from SMEs structure.

Lack of equity/capital problem, finding fund problems and financial management problems are the problems that constitute financial problems of SMEs in having loan [8]. Not using the alternative financial techniques can also be added to these problems.

Loan problems faced; in order to continue their activities SMEs should either use their equity or have loan from a bank. Because the SMEs are established with a limited capital, financing through loan to bank is important. Using loan intensively and effectively by SMEs is important for both their survival and sustainable economic growth in the country. Having loan from banks is of vital importance in our country but unfortunately the share SMEs get is very small [9].

SMEs work with a limited capital that they cannot show the assurance banks expect. In addition, their financial statement cannot meet the requirements. For that reason, banks prefer to work with big businesses [7]. When SMEs have loan, they have to face higher interest rates, banks want to take less risk for that reason they ask for some assurance. While big businesses show their assets as assurance, the owner of small businesses shows their personal estates as assurance.

Business owner faces to lose his all assets falling down on the job. This situation leads small businesses behave timidly in financing through loan [10].

Problems caused from inadequate equity/capital; there are two main ways to finance the activities of businesses. The first one is using their own sources (equity) and the second one is to meet this need having loan from a bank. Businesses need venture fund during establishment phase and working fund (current assets- short-term loans). Equity can be obtained from shareholders or capital market. SMEs in our country cannot benefit from capital market much [11]. It is known that SMEs do not use bank loans a lot, which means equity, comes into prominence. For that reason, the businesses founded with equity are hard up. Especially, during economic fluctuations, businesses face cash problem. In process of time, businesses tend towards external sources, use higher rate bank loans and not being able to manage their investment, they go bankruptcy [12].

The structural problems encountered during having fund from capital market; having fund from capital market is an important financial alternative for the SMEs which have difficulty in getting loan and do not have enough equity.

SMEs can have fund having bill of exchange, bill of exchange replaceable with share certificate, participation bond, participating shares, profit and loss sharing certificate, profit and loss sharing certificate replaceable with share certificate and financial bill [13]. As it is stated before, capital market is an important source of finance for SMEs but they do not benefit. The main reasons of this situation can be [14]:

- Being individual or family owned SMEs and fear of losing managing power
- The cost of going public
- Being small sized enterprise
- Organizational structure and account systems of SMEs
- SMEs expecting to be off the records

The traditional mentality of SMEs managers “management is our job and nobody should interfere”, the independent amount of money SMEs pay while going public, advertisement cost, share certificate press, notice and announcement costs, sales commission; thinking that small businesses will not avail, not having expected organization and account systems that foreseen by capital market and being off the book avoiding paying taxes are the important obstacles Small and Medium scale businesses encounter in getting into the market.

The problems caused by inadequate financial management; inadequate financial information and not being able to use the modern financial techniques are among the micro problems of SMEs. Not having a separate finance department, not having enough information about finance and not hiring finance experts for the work deepens the problem of SMEs [15].

Not using the financial techniques enough: SMEs finance their own sources on their own and use the loan taken from banks after the equity. In the following table, it is seen that SMEs do not use Eximbank, Europe Investment Bank, financial institutions, leasing and factoring as financial sources. SMEs’ using their equity or having loan from bank market hem do not benefit the other types of financial sources [16]. In the rest of the study, a field study at a previously determined destination is given.

V. THE AIM, SCOPE AND METHOD OF THE STUDY

In most of the studies conducted in Turkey, financial problems are among the problems of businesses in the first place. Particularly, equity capital and external source problems, high cost and inadequate credit issues are the problems encountered during the establishment phase. This situation creates problems in terms of business retention and motivation

In this study, it is aimed

- To determine financial problems and sources,
- To purpose alternative solutions for the existing problems

Of the tourism businesses which have an undeniable share in the city economy it operates and their share in tourism sector. This study aims to determine the current situation, developmental condition and the problems especially the financial ones that hotels and travel agencies in the cities of Central Anatolia encounter while carrying their activities. As a result of the study, no discrimination is made between the

businesses and their legal status of the businesses operating in the cities of Central Anatolia. Survey method is used in data collection. Before preparing the questionnaire, related literature is searched, similar subjects and research methods are investigated and the data obtained from the employers were considered in finalizing the form. Within the scope of research, the survey was applied to service sector. Questions asked in the questionnaire were mostly for determining the financial problems encountered by the tourism businesses. The survey consists of single section and has questions about the structure, legal statue and demographic information about the staff of the business to determine the general management problems and financial problems. Survey method was taken from an article at the Magazine of Faculty of Economic and Administrative Sciences, Kafkas University, Volume: 3 Issue: 3 Year: 2012. In order to create the questionnaire, data was obtained after visiting 25 businesses in person and through emails. The data obtained from the people in businesses were analyzed using Microsoft Excel.

VI. THE RESULTS AND EVALUATION OF RESEARCH

As seen in Table I, 13 of the managements (52%) implemented the survey are the hotel business and 12 of them (48%) are the travel business.

10 of the businesses (40%) operate in Konya, 8 (32%) in Ankara, 3 (12%) in the Cappadocia region of Nevsehir, 2 (8%) in Eskisehir, and 2 (8%) in Sivas. In terms of its legal situations, 12 of the businesses (48%) consist of personal business, 7 (28%) of corporation, 3 (12%) of unlimited, 2 (8%) of limited, and 1 (4%) of unincorporated. When the employment rates of the businesses surveyed are treated, the number of business employed between 1-9 is 1 (4%), the number of business employed between 10-39 is 11 (44%), the number of business employed between 40-69 is 9 (36%), and the number of business employed between 70-100 is 5 (20%). There is not any business employing 100 or more. 2 of 25 businesses (8%) surveyed operate for 0-5 years, 11(44%) for 6-10 years, 9 (36%) for 11-14 years, and 2 (8%) for 15-19 years. The number of businesses operating for 20 years and more is 1 (4%). When the information obtained by those contributing to the survey is analysed, the number of business answering that the business owner is the business manager at the same time is 12 businesses (48%), the number of the business employing an outside property manager is 8 (32%), and the number of the business managed by chairman of the board is 5 (20%). According to the information gotten from the businesses contributing to the survey, there are 4 (16%) managers whose educational level is postgraduate, 19 (76%) whose level is undergraduate, and 2 (8%) whose level is high school among the most senior executives.

Departments in the Business

All businesses surveyed have a managerial unit. 23 businesses (92%) have the accounting department, 20 businesses (80%) have the department of sales and marketing, 17 businesses (68%) have the department of human resources, 16 businesses (64%) have the purchasing department, 13

businesses (52%) have the department of front office, 13 businesses (52%) have the department of food and beverage, 7 businesses (28%) have the department of planning and control, and 4 businesses (16%) have the R&D department.

TABLE I
DEMOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION

Type of Business	n	%
Travel Business	12	48
Hotel Business	13	52
	100	
Cities in which the businesses are	n	%
Konya	10	40
Ankara	8	32
Nevsehir	3	12
Sivas	2	8
Eskisehir	2	8
	100	
The legal situations of the businesses	n	%
Person	12	48
Corporation	7	28
Unlimited	3	12
Limited	2	8
Unincorporated	1	4
	100	
Number of staff	n	%
1-9	1	4
10-39	10	40
40-69	9	36
70-100	5	20
100+	0	0
	100	
Operating Period	n	%
0-5	2	8
6-10	11	44
11-14	9	36
15-19	2	8
20+	1	4
	100	
Business Management	n	%
Business Owner	12	48
Outside Property Manager	8	32
Chairman of the Board	5	20
	100	
The educational level of business managers	n	%
Postgraduate	4	16
Undergraduate	19	76
High School	2	8
	100	

TABLE II
DEPARTMENT IN BUSINESSES

Departments	Existing		Not-Existing	
	n	%	n	%
Management	25	100	0	0
Accounting	23	92	2	8
Sales and Marketing	20	80	5	20
Human Resources	17	68	8	32
Purchasing	16	64	9	36
Front Office	13	52	12	48
Food and Beverage	13	52	12	48
Planning and Control	7	28	18	72
R & D	4	16	21	84

The Problems that the Businesses Experience in the Phase of Establishment

From the businesses surveyed, 13 businesses (52%) face

with the deficiency of equity, 5 (20%) with the lack of knowledge, 4 (16%) with the rise of credit costs, and 3 (12%) with the problems of qualified personnel in the phase of the establishment of business as seen in Table I, 13 of the managements (52%) implemented the survey are the hotel business and 12 of them (48%) are the travel business as seen in Table I, 13 of the managements (52%) implemented the survey are the hotel business and 12 of them (48%) are the travel business.

TABLE III
THE PROBLEMS THAT THE BUSINESSES EXPERIENCE IN THE PHASE OF ESTABLISHMENT

Financial Targets	n	%
Deficiency of Equity	13	52
Lack of Knowledge	5	20
Rise of Credit Costs	4	16
Problem of Qualified Personnel	3	12
	100	

The Situation of Doing Feasibility in the Phase of Establishment of the Business

From the businesses surveyed, 14 businesses (56%) answer that feasibility study is done, 6 businesses (24%) that feasibility study is not done, and 5 businesses (20%) that feasibility study is partly done.

TABLE IV
WAS THE FEASIBILITY STUDY DONE IN THE PHASE OF ESTABLISHMENT?

Was the Feasibility Study done in the Phase of Establishment	n	%
Yes	14	56
No	6	24
Partly	5	20
	100	

The Authority of Taking Financial Decisions in the Businesses

From the businesses; 12 (48%) of the businesses surveyed answer that financial decisions are taken by the business owner, 8 businesses (32%) by the department of administrative affairs (directors of department), and 5 businesses (20%) by the board of directors.

TABLE V
THE AUTHORITY OF TAKING FINANCIAL DECISIONS IN THE BUSINESS

The Authority of Taking Financial Decisions	n	%
Business Owner	12	48
Administrative Affairs (Directors of Department)	8	32
Board of Directors	5	20
	100	

The Financial Goal of Businesses for the Future

It is determined in the financial goals for future that the goal of 14 businesses (56%) of the businesses surveyed is to expand and grow its company, 5 businesses (20%) to the leader in its sector, 12 businesses (12%) to hold the market, and 3 businesses to ensure a better income.

The Maturity Period Preferred by the Businesses in the Use of Bank Loans

10 businesses (40%) of the businesses surveyed prefer the long-term bank loan and 7 businesses (28%) prefer the medium term. 8 businesses (32%) do not use any bank loan.

TABLE VI
THE FINANCIAL GOALS OF COMPANY

Financial Goals	n	%
To Expand and Grow the Company	14	56
To be the Leader in the Sector	5	20
To Hold the Market	3	12
To Ensure a Better Income	3	12
	100	

TABLE VII
THE MATURITY PERIOD PREFERRED BY THE BUSINESSES IN THE USE OF BANK LOANS

Maturity Period Preferred	n	%
Long-Term	10	40
Medium-Term	7	28
Not Using Any Bank Loan	8	32
	100	

The Problems that the Businesses Experience in the Procurement of the Bank Loan

From the businesses surveyed; 9 businesses (36%) show Balance and the shortage of Income Statement in the procurement of bank loan as the reason, 5 businesses (20%) show the lack of deposit, 3 businesses (12%) show the rise of the high interest rates. In addition, 8 businesses (32%) do not use any bank loan.

TABLE VIII
THE PROBLEMS THAT THE BUSINESSES EXPERIENCE IN THE PROCUREMENT OF THE BANK LOAN

The Problems Experienced	n	%
Balance, the Shortage of Income Statement	9	36
The Lack of Deposit	5	20
The Rise of the High Interest Rates	3	12
Not Using Any Bank Loan	8	32
	100	

The Financial Techniques that the Businesses Take Advantage

From the Businesses surveyed; 5 businesses (20%) mark the leasing technique and 2 businesses (8%) mark the factoring technique. Moreover, 18 businesses (72%) state not to benefit from any financial technique.

TABLE IX
THE FINANCIAL TECHNIQUES THAT THE BUSINESSES TAKE ADVANTAGE

Financial Techniques Taking Advantage	n	%
Leasing	5	20
Factoring	2	8
Not Benefitting from any Technique	18	72
	100	

The Five-Year Written Goals of the Business

It is determined that 15 businesses (60%) of the businesses surveyed have not any written goal, 7 businesses (28%) have a five-year written goal, and 3 businesses (12%) have a partly-written five-year goal.

TABLE X
THE FIVE-YEAR WRITTEN GOALS OF THE BUSINESS

The Situation of Five-Year Written Goal	n	%
Not Having Any Written Goal	15	60
Having a Written Goal	7	28
Having a Partly-Written Goal	3	12
	100	

The Adequacy Status of Equity of the Businesses

It is fixed that 9 businesses (36%) of the businesses surveyed have an adequate equity, 4 businesses (16%) have not an adequate equity, and 1 business (4%) has a partly adequate equity. 11 businesses (44%) state not to have any idea about the subject.

TABLE XI
THE ADEQUACY STATUS OF EQUITY OF THE BUSINESSES

The Adequacy Status of Equity	n	%
Having an Adequate Equity	9	36
Not Having an Adequate Equity	4	16
Partly-Having an Adequate Equity	1	4
Having No Idea	11	44
		100

The Assessment Method of the Profit that the Businesses Obtain by Their Activities

From the businesses surveyed, 13 businesses (52%) prefer to add the profit obtained into the capital, 7 businesses (28%) distribute the profit obtained to the shareholders, 4 businesses (16%) purchase the real estate, and 1 business (4%) makes new investments.

TABLE XII
THE ASSESSMENT METHOD OF THE PROFIT THAT THE BUSINESSES OBTAIN BY THEIR ACTIVITIES

The Assessment Method of the Profit Obtained	n	%
Adding it into the Capital	13	52
Distributing the Profit Obtained to the Shareholders	7	28
Purchasing the Real Estate	4	16
Making New Investments	1	4
		100

The Opinions of Businesses about the Promotions Toward the Sector

It is determined that 21 businesses (84%) of the businesses surveyed are in favor of the state to increase the promotions towards the sector. 3 businesses (12%) state not to have any opinion about this issue. In addition, 1 business expresses that the state make the promotion toward the sector adequately.

TABLE XIII
THE OPINIONS OF BUSINESSES ABOUT THE PROMOTIONS TOWARD THE SECTOR

Opinions about Promotions	n	%
It should be increased the promotions towards the sector	21	84
The state adequately promotes the sector	3	12
Having No Idea	1	4
		100

The Regional Marketing Strategies towards the Tourism Sector

It is determined that 22 businesses (88%) of the businesses surveyed support the constitution of regional marketing strategies towards the sector and 3 businesses (12%) have not any idea related to the issue.

The Utilization Status of Benefitting from the Consulting Services

It is fixed that 10 businesses (40%) of the businesses surveyed receive a service from a consulting organization and 15 businesses (60) do not receive a service from any expert

organization.

TABLE XIV
THE REGIONAL MARKETING STRATEGIES TOWARDS THE TOURISM SECTOR

Regional Marketing Strategies	n	%
Those Supporting the Constitution of Strategies	22	88
Having No Idea	3	12
		100

TABLE XV
THE UTILIZATION STATUS OF BENEFITTING FROM THE CONSULTING SERVICES

Consulting Services	n	%
Benefitting	10	40
Not Benefitting	15	60
		100

The General Issues Related to the Sector

It is determined that 9 businesses (36%) of the businesses surveyed have the problems to be urgently solved in the field of finance, 7 businesses (28%) in the legal field, 4 businesses (16%) in the field of the employment of qualified staff, 3 businesses (12%) in the managerial field, and 2 businesses (8%) in the field of sufficient advertising.

TABLE XVI
THE ISSUES RELATED TO THE SECTOR

The Fields considered as having the problem in the sector	n	%
Finance	9	36
Law	7	28
Employment of Qualified Staff	4	16
Managerial Problems	3	12
Insufficient Advertising	2	8
		100

VII. CONCLUSION

The problems of tourism businesses in Turkey are almost the same. It is observed that the problems differing from sector to sector encounter financial and political problems. As the law does not protect the businesses and the activities to attract tourists cause a decrease in both service quality and “quality tourist”. The foreigners who rented a house and settled our country caused a situation that can be called off record tourism activity. Tourism sector should be protected by law urgently and businesses and staff should be informed.

In this study, a survey is conducted with the businesses working in Central Anatolia Region in order to determine the financial problems. The problems found are as follows,

- Businesses experience problems because of lack of equity during establishment phase and the rest period.
- Because the banks have higher interest rates, the banks’ demand for assurance and the businesses’ not having the convenient features and as a result not asking for loan cause a contraction in the sector.
- Most of the businesses do not benefit from financial techniques. The business owners and executives should be informed. When the survey results considered, it is seen that most of the businesses do not get help from a professional aid agency. With an incentive and facility by the government the businesses should be professionally managed, these businesses should be helped to have at least 5-year strategic plan.

- Because most of the business managers do not have enough information about management and organization, the businesses do not have a vision and it is seen that these businesses are lack of financial planning and planned work Schedule.
- The businesses use classical financial tools and do not lionize other alternative financial techniques because they do not have enough information. When compared the other techniques, leasing is partially known but the businesses have no idea about “venture credit”, “barter” and “credit guarantee fund”.
- The businesses should not share their problems only with the same individuals and institutions, they should publish a notice through non-governmental organizations and associations in order to ask the academics and business owner’s opinions and find solution to their problems.

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